

Palladium complexes with two unsymmetrical Schiff base ligands: Highly active catalyst for activation of chloroarenes in Suzuki-Miyaura reaction

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Two new unsymmetrical Schiff base derived palladium(II) complexes, [PdCl₂{bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzamide}] (**C1**) and [PdCl₂{N,N'-bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzylamine}] (**C2**) have been synthesized and characterized. The complexes have been explored as catalysts for the Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reactions of aryl halides with arylboronic acids. An optimization study reveals that under similar experimental conditions, the complex **C1** shows superior activity over the complex **C2**. Using the complex **C1** as catalyst, less reactive chloroarenes are efficiently converted to their corresponding biaryls under relatively mild conditions (80°C, 0.5 mol% catalyst) using EtOH as an environmentally safer reaction media. Excellent yields of cross coupling products are also obtained with aryl bromides at room temperature in neat water with low catalyst loading (0.02 mol %).

Keywords: Unsymmetrical Schiff base, Pd catalyst, Suzuki-Miyaura reaction, aryl chloride, ethanol, water.

Introduction

Palladium catalyzed carbon-carbon bond formation reaction is considered to be one of the most studied methods in organic chemistry that has got several industrial applications^{1a,b}. Among various cross coupling methods, Suzuki-Miyaura reaction has got particular attention because of its excellent functional group tolerance, wide substrate scope, simple reaction conditions and generation of non-toxic boronated byproducts along with high regio and stereo-selectivity^{2,1a}. In the past few decades, there has been an exponential rise in the number of publications in the Suzuki-Miyaura coupling reactions. However, majority of these reports have dealt with aryl bromides or iodides as substrates^{3a-c}. On the contrary, highly active catalysts for efficient activation of aryl chlorides under mild conditions are very limited^{4a-d}, although from the cost and accessibility point of views aryl chlorides are the most preferred substrates compared to corresponding bromides/iodides^{5a-c}. Nevertheless, there exist a few catalytic systems that can efficiently activate aryl chlorides in Suzuki reactions, however majority of such systems either use toxic and synthetically difficult air-sensitive phosphines as ligands^{6a-c,4d} or environmentally

unsafe reaction media like DMF⁷, dioxane⁸, THF⁹, etc.

Consequently, in recent years, efforts are being given to develop alternative systems comprised of non-toxic and air stable ligands like N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs)^{10a,b}, Schiff bases^{11a-c,3a}, thiosemicarbazones¹², etc. for cross-coupling reactions. Among these systems, from the cost and synthetic accessibility point of views, Schiff bases are found to be the most effective ligand system^{13a,b}. Like phosphines, the stereo-electronic property in Schiff bases can easily be tuned by choosing the right condensing partners (aldehydes and amines)^{14,3a}.

It is noteworthy to mention that there are a few reports about Schiff base derived Pd catalysts that show excellent cross coupling activity with aryl halides including aryl chlorides in Suzuki-Miyaura reactions^{15a-e}. However, in most of those systems, the Schiff base ligands are based on symmetric functionalization of diamines^{16a-c}, while unsymmetrical Schiff bases are expected to provide more interesting chemistry in catalytical perspective. Very recently, Sedighipour *et al.*^{13a} reported a palladium complex with unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base ligand that shows excellent cross-coupling activities with a few aryl bromides,

however the catalytic system fails to promote aryl chlorides as substrates.

Herein, to explore the potentiality of unsymmetrical Schiff base ligands, we have synthesized two Schiff base ligands and their Pd complexes. The catalytic activities of the complexes have been investigated for the Suzuki-Miyaura reactions of aryl chlorides and bromides with arylboronic acids using environment friendly reaction media such as EtOH and water.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

PdCl₂ and salicylaldehyde were purchased from Spectrochem. The substrates for Suzuki reaction were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Spectrochem and TCI whereas the solvents of analytical grade were purchased from Rankem. All the solvents were distilled and dried prior to use. The amines used in the synthesis of ligands were bought from TCI. The mass spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in ES⁺ mode using Waters ZQ-4000 LC-MS. FT-IR (400–4000 cm⁻¹) spectra were recorded in KBr using Shimadzu, Prestige-21 IR spectrophotometer. The NMR (¹H and ¹³C) spectra of the compounds were recorded using Bruker Avance II 400 MHz spectrometer. The percentage yields of the products have been determined with GC (Perkin-Elmer-Clarus 480) with Flame Ionization Detector. Confirmation and quantification of products were done with respect to authentic samples.

Synthesis of ligands:

A solution of salicylaldehyde (0.488 g, 4 mmol) in 20 mL EtOH was added dropwise to the solution of anthranilamide (0.272 g, 2 mmol) and 2-aminobenzylamine (0.408 g, 2 mmol) respectively in 10 mL of EtOH. The mixtures were stirred under refluxing conditions for 4 h (Scheme 1). The precipitates thus formed were washed with cold ethanol and dried in vacuum to obtain the pure ligands.

Synthesis of complexes:

A solution of the ligand bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzamide (**L-01**) (0.258 g, 0.75 mmol) or N,N'-bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzylamine (**L-02**) (0.248 g, 0.75 mmol) in acetonitrile (10 mL) was added dropwise to a solution of PdCl₂ (0.75 mmol, 0.133 g) dissolved in acetonitrile (10 mL) and the mixture was stirred at 70°C for 3 h. The solution was filtered and the solvent was evaporated from the filtrate to

get the solid product. The obtained compounds were washed with diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. The complex **C1** was isolated as brown solid (Yield 84%) whereas the complex **C2** was orange in colour (Yield 88%).

General procedure for Suzuki-Miyaura reactions:

A 50 mL round-bottom flask was charged with aryl halide (0.5 mmol), arylboronic acid (0.65 mmol), base (1.5 mmol) and the Pd catalyst. The mixture was stirred for a particular time at appropriate temperatures for chlorides and room temperature for bromides in EtOH and H₂O (4 mL) respectively. The progress of the reaction was monitored by GC. After completion, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and diluted with 20 mL water and extracted with diethylether (3×15 mL). The extract was washed with brine (3×15 mL) and dried over Na₂SO₄. After evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure, the residue was chromatographed (silica gel, ethyl acetate-hexane, 1:9) to obtain the desired product. The identities of the products were confirmed by ¹H NMR spectral analysis.

Results and discussion

Syntheses and characterizations of ligands and complexes:

The ligands N,N'-bis(salicylidene)-aminobenzamide (**L-01**) and N,N'-bis(salicylidene)-2-aminobenzylamine (**L-02**) are synthesized by reacting two equivalents of salicylaldehyde with one equivalent of anthranilamide and 2-aminobenzylamine respectively in EtOH under reflux condition (Scheme 1). In the FT-IR spectra, the ν_{C=N} stretching was observed at 1608 cm⁻¹ and 1624 cm⁻¹ for the ligands **L-01** and **L-02** respectively. The ν_{C=O} band in the ligand **L-01** appears at 1648 cm⁻¹. As the ligands are unsymmetrical in nature, two singlets for imine protons in the ¹H NMR spectra are observed. In the case of ligand **L-01**, two peaks are observed at δ 9.85 and 7.93 ppm, while for the ligand **L-02**, the peaks are observed at δ 8.55 and 8.44 ppm. The relatively downfield shift of one of the imine protons in the ligand **L-01** was due to the presence of carbonyl groups attached to imine. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of the ligand **L-01** also shows two peaks for imine carbons at δ 154.57 and 148.10 ppm along with the carbonyl peak at δ 187.85 ppm.

The Pd complexes, **C1** and **C2** are prepared by the reaction of the ligands **L-01** and **L-02** respectively with PdCl₂ in acetonitrile for 3 h at 70°C (Scheme 1). The mass spectra of

the complex **C1** shows a peak at m/z : 518, 563 and 585 attributed to the $[M-2H]^+$, $[M+K+2H]^+$ $[M+K+Na+H]^+$ ions respectively. Similarly, mass spectra of the complex **C2** shows a peak at 527 for $[M+NH_4+H]^+$ ion.

In the FT-IR spectrum of complex **C1**, the $\nu_{C=N}$ stretching bands appeared at 1580 cm^{-1} and 1604 cm^{-1} . Compared to the free ligand, a prominent shift has been observed towards lower wave number indicating complexation through the imine group. The presence of two different $\nu_{C=N}$ bands in the complex might be attributed to the unsymmetrical nature of the ligand. Similar to the complex **C1**, the FT-IR spectrum of complex **C2** also shows two $\nu_{C=N}$ bands at 1614 and 1572 cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR spectrum of complex **C1** shows two singlets for the -OH protons at δ 13.29 and 13.20 ppm and two singlets for the imine protons at δ 11.75 and 10.24 ppm. Compared to the free ligand **L-01**, the peaks are shifted to downfield indicating coordination through imine. In the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **C1**, the imine carbon peaks are found to appear at δ 159.47 and 154.17 ppm which are significantly downfield compared to corresponding free ligand peak. The carbonyl carbon is observed at δ 191.67 ppm. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the complex **C2**, showed the imine carbons at δ 164.83 and 163.69 ppm.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of complexes **C1** and **C2**.

Catalytic application in Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reaction:

In order to evaluate the catalytic activity of the complexes for Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reaction, 4-chloroanisole and phenylboronic acid are chosen as model substrates. Ir-

respective of solvent systems, under similar experimental conditions, the complex **C1** has shown superior results over the complex **C2** (Table 1). An initial solvent optimization study with both the complexes (Table 1) reveals that EtOH (Entry 5) and DMF (Entry 9) are the two best solvent systems; however considering greener perspective, we have chosen EtOH as the reaction media for further study. The optimization of temperature and catalyst quantity has shown that the optimum condition for the reaction is 80°C , 0.5 mol% catalyst (Table 1, entry 5). To investigate the effect of bases in our reactions we have checked a few inorganic bases and found that K_2CO_3 is the best candidate for the study.

Table 1. Screening of the complexes as catalysts for the Suzuki-Miyaura reaction of 4-chloroanisole with phenylboronic acid

Entry	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Cat. (mol%)	Yield (%) ^a	
				Complex C1	Complex C2
1	DCM	RT	0.5	43	37
2	Acetone	RT	0.5	47	40
3	EtOH	RT	0.5	41	16
4	EtOH	50	0.5	48	24
5	EtOH	80	0.5	94	70
6	EtOH	80	0.2	52	23
7	H ₂ O	80	0.5	28	18
8	EtOH:H ₂ O ^b	80	0.5	72	58
9	DMF	80	0.5	100	97

Reaction conditions: 4-Chloroanisole (0.5 mmol), phenylboronic acid (0.65 mmol), K_2CO_3 (1.5 mmol), solvent (4 mL). ^aGC yield. ^bsolvents in 1:1 ratio.

To investigate the effects of different substrates in our catalytic system, we have used a wide range of electronically and sterically diverse aryl chlorides under the optimized conditions. We are gratified to see that the complex **C1** effectively converts aryl chlorides containing electron withdrawing substituent like -CHO or (Table 2, entry 4) as well as electron donating substituents like -CH₃, -OCH₃ (Table 2, entries 1 and 2) at *para*-position into corresponding biaryls in moderate-to-excellent yields. It may be noted that our catalyst is also very effective with more challenging substrates like sterically hindered *ortho*-substituted aryl chlorides. For instance, the reaction of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (Table 2, entry 6) with phenylboronic acid gives 63% yield of the desired product. The complex **C1** has also shown efficient catalytic

Table 2. Suzuki-Miyaura reactions of various aryl and heteroaryl chlorides and arylboronic acids using complex **C1** as catalyst
$$\text{R}-\text{Cl} + \text{R}'-\text{B}(\text{OH})_2 \xrightarrow[\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3, \text{EtOH}, 60^\circ\text{C}]{\text{C1 (0.5 mol\%)}} \text{R}-\text{R}'$$

Entry	R-Cl	R'-B(OH) ₂	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^a
1		5	90	
2		6	87	
3		6	88	
4		6	78	
5		6	85	
6		8	63	
7		8	88	
8		8	85	
9		8	88	

Reaction conditions: Aryl chloride (0.5 mmol), arylboronic acid (0.65 mmol), K₂CO₃ (1.5 mmol), EtOH (4 mL). ^aGC yield.

activity with heteroaryl chloride viz. 3-chloropyridine (Table 2, entry 7) with coupling product yield of 88%.

The efficiency of the complex **C1** has also been evaluated for relatively easier substrates like aryl bromides at room temperature. For this purpose, 4-bromoanisole and phenylboronic acid are chosen as model substrates to optimize the catalyst quantity. It has been observed that 0.02 mol% of the complex **C1** is sufficient for significant conversion of the substrates into the desired biaryls in water using K₂CO₃ as base. It is noteworthy to mention that we have followed a green protocol to synthesize C-C coupled using aqueous media.

Like aryl chlorides, in this case also we have examined a range of electronically diverse aryl bromides. The catalyst **C1** is found to be highly tolerant for the substrates with a broad range of functional groups. *para*-substituted aryl bromides having electron-donating (Table 3, entries 1 and 3) as well as electron withdrawing substituents (Table 3, entry 2) have coupled to give desired products with excellent yields (92–94%) in water. Excellent yields are also obtained with sterically hindered substrates viz. 2-bromo-1,4-dimethoxy benzene (Table 3, entry 4) and also for heteroaryl bromides (Table 3, entries 6 and 7). In addition to phenylboronic acid, the catalyst is found to tolerate other arylboronic acids with

Table 3. Room temperature Suzuki-Miyaura reactions of various aryl bromides with arylboronic acids with the complex **C1** as catalyst
$$\text{R}-\text{Br} + \text{R}'-\text{B}(\text{OH})_2 \xrightarrow[\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{RT}]{\text{C1 (0.02 mol\%)}} \text{R}-\text{R}'$$

Entry	R-Br	R'-B(OH) ₂	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^a
1		6	94	
2		8	92	
3		8	93	
4		8	87	
5		10	82	
6		6	93	
7		6	94	
8		8	95	

Reaction conditions: Aryl halide (0.5 mmol), arylboronic acid (0.65 mmol), K₂CO₃ (1.5 mmol), H₂O (4 mL). ^aGC yield.

Table 4. Comparative study on Schiff base derived Pd-catalyst for Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reactions

Entry	Schiff base	Substrate	Solvent	Temp./ Time (h)	Catalyst mol%	Yield (%)	Ref.
1	Unsymmetrical N ₂ O ₂ -type	<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	H ₂ O	RT/6	0.02	94	Present
		<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	EtOH	80°C/5	0.50	90	work
2	Sulfonamide Schiff base	<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	H ₂ O	RT/2	0.02	99	14
		<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	<i>i</i> PrOH	60°C/12	1.0	88	
3	Bidentate N ₂ -type	<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	DMF	100°C/4	0.2	86	16(a)
4	Water-soluble N,O-type	<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	H ₂ O	RT/8	0.2	97	15(e)
		<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	H ₂ O	100°C/5	1.0	93	
5	Tetradentate N ₄ -type	<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	H ₂ O Glycerol-	RT/12	0.2	99	16(b)
		<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	H ₂ O (1:1)	80°C/12	1.0	74	
6	Tetradentate N ₂ O ₂ -type	<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	H ₂ O	50°C/15m	0.2	95	5(d)
		<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	<i>i</i> PrOH	50°C/2	1.0	75	

significant yield of the desired product (Table 3, entries 7 and 8). For aryl bromides these results are quite significant because of the use of environmentally-benign reaction media from green point of view.

It is worth to highlight again that there exist some reports about successful uses of Schiff base derived Pd-catalysts for the Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reactions, however, to understand the actual status of our catalytic system in comparison with reported catalysts, we have performed a literature survey of reported Schiff base catalysts taking the reaction between *p*-haloanisole and phenylboronic acid as a model example (Table 4). We are delighted to note that our present unsymmetrical-Schiff base derived catalytic system seems much superior comparison to the reported systems. For instance, most of the reported systems required 0.2 mol% and 1 mol% catalyst quantities for *p*-bromoanisole and *p*-chloroanisole, however in our present system we have used ten times and two times less catalyst quantity for aryl bromides and chlorides respectively.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have developed a simple and highly efficient catalytic system containing unsymmetrical Schiff base ligands for Suzuki-Miyaura reactions of aryl halides with aryl boronic acids. Challenging substrates like chloroarenes could be efficiently converted to their corresponding biaryls under relatively mild conditions in EtOH, while relatively easier substrates like aryl bromides could be converted even at room temperature in H₂O with a very low catalyst loading (0.02 mol%).

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